

Center for Composite Materials

Transverse Shear Characterization of Aligned Discontinuous Fiber Prepregs using Squeeze Flow

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TuFF Introduction

TuFF: Tailored Universal Feedstock for Forming

- **Chopped fibers** are highly **aligned** by water flow onto thin film
- Films of aligned fiber are prepregged with resin
- Prepreg can be used in **thermoforming process**
 - **Allows for stretch** during forming
 - Final properties comparable to continuous unidirectional prepreg

Outline

- Motivation
- Objectives
- Test Methodology
- Results and Future Work

Motivation

Motivation

Forming:

TuFF Blank

Tool displacement rate,
Temperature

or

Gas pressure,
Temperature

Motivation

Forming:

5 main deformation mechanisms:

Motivation

Forming:

5 main deformation mechanisms:

Virtual Modeling:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \eta_P \cdot \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}C_{11} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

Stresses = Polymer viscosity · Directional magnification from fibers · Strain rates

Objectives

Constitutive model to describe TuFF Deformation in Aniform

- Develop an anisotropic material model to relate the **stress**(σ) vs **strain rate** ($\dot{\epsilon}$) for forming.
- Magnification matrix modifies **polymer viscosity**.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \eta_P \cdot \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}C_{11} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

Stresses = Polymer viscosity · Directional magnification from fibers · Strain rates

Effect of C_{66} on Biased Extension Test

$\uparrow C_{66} = 1e2$
 $\downarrow \epsilon_{LT} = 0.27$

$1e3$
 0.21

$1e4$
 0.16

$1e5$
 0.04

$1e6 \sim C_{11}$
 0.005

Test Methodology

Experimental Procedure

Experimental Procedure

≈ 30 Minute hold

Remove voids

Constant displacement rate (\dot{h}) Oven

$$h_{consolidation} = \frac{\text{Sample mass}}{\text{TuFF density} \times \text{Fixture area}} \approx 4.3\text{mm}$$

Experimental Procedure

Constant displacement rate (\dot{h}) Oven

Squeeze Flow Experiment to Determine C_{66}

Consolidate sample:

Drive squeeze flow:

Squeeze flow creates a **shearing deformation** in the sample which allows C_{66} to be characterized

Squeeze Flow Visualization with Markers

- Initial **parabolic** flow -> no slip boundary condition at **TuFF-tool** interface
- Analytical solution for force available from dimensions, viscosity (η), and closing rate (\dot{h})

$$F = \frac{4 L^3 W \eta \dot{h}}{h^3}$$

- Transition to plug or partial slip flow → evidence of **interfacial slip** developing at the TuFF-tool interface in later stages of the test

Model Formulation

- TuFF prepreg in squeeze flow is not only a viscous reaction, acts like a **spring and damper** system when squeezed:

Viscous Resin Force:

$$F_{Resin} = \frac{4L^3W\dot{h}\eta_p C_{66}}{h^3}$$

Spring Fiber Force:

$$F_{Fiber} = \sum_{i=1}^n k_i (h_o - h)^i$$

- The addition of these two reaction forces will describe the no slip portion of the experiment

$$F_{Sample} = F_{Resin} + F_{Fibers}$$

- h_o has been selected to be the displacement where the force begins to increase at $h = 4.68mm$

1. Motivation

2. Objectives

3. Test methodology

4. Results and Future Work

Results and Future Work

Squeeze Flow Experimental Results

- Squeeze flow experiments produce repeatable results

Modeling The Spring Response

- To fully describe spring response, sample squeezed to consecutive displacements
- Fiber spring response tracked

Fiber Response:

$$F_{Fibers} = 0.44(4.68 - h)^4$$

Fitted Parameters

- By isolating the viscous response to squeeze flow, C_{66} can be found using least squares optimization.
- For characterization to be correct, C_{66} remain constant at different dimensions and closure rates

$$F = \frac{4L^3W\dot{h}\eta_P C_{66}}{h^3} + k_4(h_o - h)^4$$

Parameters:

C_{66} : 17853

k_4 : 0.44

- Prepreg viscosity is 18000 time larger than the polymer viscosity

Summary

- A model was formulated to characterize the transvers viscosity of TuFF prepreg.
- Squeeze flow experiments were conducted in a 2"x1" fixture, all fibers were aligned in the direction perpendicular to flow.
- Three consistent experiments were performed and the viscosity was found to be 1e4 times larger than the polymer viscosity.
- Same methodology will be used to find viscosity using 4"x1" fixture.
- The characterized value will be used in Aniform.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \eta_P \cdot \begin{bmatrix} D_{11}C_{11} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} \dot{\epsilon}_{11} \\ \dot{\epsilon}_{22} \\ \dot{\gamma}_{12} \end{bmatrix}$$

Stresses = Polymer viscosity • Directional magnification from fibers • Strain rates

Fitted Parameters

- There have been two different sample dimensions tested, 4"x1" and 2"x1"
- Even with varying dimensions, C_{66} should be the same between experiments

$$F = \frac{4L^3W\dot{h}\eta_P C_{66}}{h^3} + k_1(h_o - h) + k_3(h_o - h)^3$$

2"x1" Fixture Fit

4"x1" Fixture Fit

Parameters:

C_{66} : 3940

k_1 : 1.66

k_2 : 1.22

Parameters:

C_{66} : 2850

k_1 : 3.38

k_3 : 1.66

Other Method for Defining the Spring Response

- Residual force is taken from consolidation and final displacement
- Polynomial spring is created and then C_{66} is found

Spring Equation

$$k_1(h_o - h) + k_3(h_o - h)^3$$

